

Studies on Thiazolidinones: Part IV. Thiazolidinones and Their Derivatives Derived from Unsymmetrical Thioureas

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Synthesis of 2-(benzothiazolylimino-2') 3-phenyl 4-thiazolidinone (I; $\phi = C_7H_4NS$), 2-(4'-phenyl thiazolylimino-2') 3-phenyl 4-thiazolidinone (I; $\phi = C_6H_5NS$) and 2-(pyridylimino-2') 3-phenyl 4-thiazolidinone (I; $\phi = \text{pyridyl}$) were made from their respective thiocarbamides with mono-chloro acetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate. The thiazolidinones have been condensed with several aromatic aldehydes and the resulting arylidene derivatives have been brominated.

2-ALKYL and 2-aryl thiazolidinones and their derivatives, which are of significant therapeutic and industrial importance have been studied extensively. But relatively few compounds containing this ring with a heterocyclic substituent in the position 2 are known. Therefore in continuation of our previous work on thiazolidinone derivatives¹⁻² it was considered worthwhile to synthesise thiazolidinones and their derivatives with both heterocyclic and aromatic substituents in the positions 2 and 3 respectively. In the present investigation three different thiocarbamides were synthesised by condensing 2-amino 4-phenyl thiazole, 2-amino benzothiazole and 2-amino pyridine with phenyl isothiocyanate. These thiocarbamides were condensed with mono-chloro acetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in alcohol to furnish the thiazolidinones. Since the thiol form the thiocarbamide is responsible for the formation of thiazolidinone, it is expected that two products (I and II) will be obtained after the condensation. But in the present investigation we have got not only one product, which

the samples were further confirmed by the hydrolysis of the thiazolidinones with alcoholic hydrochloric acid. When the product, obtained by the condensation of N'-(4-phenyl thiazolyl-2) N²-phenyl thiocarbamide and mono chloroacetic acid was hydrolysed, with alcoholic HCl, the filtrate, after separation of thiazolidinone on basification gave 2-amino 4-phenyl thiazole (m.p. 151°). Similarly the other two thiazolidinones gave 2-amino benzothiazole (m.p. 130°) and 2-amino pyridine (m.p. 51°) after the hydrolysis. From these three thiazolidinones, the same thiazolidinone (m.p. 200°-201°) was also obtained, which proved that in an unsymmetrical thiocarbamide, the thiolisation will be favoured from the nitrogen atom of the heterocyclic moiety leading to the formation of the compound I and not II. This experimental fact is further substantiated from the concept of hydrogen bonding and the development of formal charge.

was confirmed from TLC as it gave a single spot in benzene and acetic acid (3:1). The authenticity of

If the thiolisation is favoured from the vicinity of aromatic nitrogen (III), it will be stabilised by the loss of aromatic character of the phenyl ring. On the other hand, if the reverse thiolisation is favoured (IV) heterocyclic ring nitrogen atom will acquire a formal negative charge. Since N⁻ is more stable than C⁻ the second mode of thiolisation is favourable. In structure IV, there is the possibility of hydrogen bonding (-S-H...N) and the result-

ing six membered ring remains in the plane of the heterocyclic ring but in structure III, the hydrogen bonding is absent as coplanarity is not possible due to ($-\text{NH}-\overset{\text{I}}{\text{C}}-$) nitrogen-carbon single bond.

The thiazolidinones have been condensed with various aromatic aldehydes in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and acetic acid and the resulting arylidene derivatives (V) have been brominated to VI.

Pharmacological test: The thiazolidinone (I; $\phi =$ benzothiazolyl) and its arylidene derivative have been screened against *A. tuberculiensis* and *S. typhi* and found to possess no activity at 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration. However, the arylidene derivative (V; pyridyl-2, $\text{R} = -\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) possesses activity against *T. mentagraphytes* at 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. IR of the compounds were taken in hexa-chloro-butadiene in Perkin Elmer 257 grating Spectrophotometer.

***N'*-phenyl *N*²-(benzothiazolyl-2) thiocarbamide:** A solution of 2-amino benzothiazole (7.5 g) and phenyl isothiocyanate (6.8 g, 65 ml) in rectified spirit (20 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 30 min. After cooling the crystalline thiocarbamide separated, which was recrystallised from aqueous alcohol. Yield -75%, m.p. 202°. (Found: C; 58.42, H; 3.53, N; 14.36; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$ requires C; 58.88, H; 3.86, N; 14.73), $\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})$ 1610 (C = N), 3300 (NH-broad).

***N'*-Phenyl *N*²-(4-phenyl thiazolyl-2) thiocarbamide:** An alcoholic solution of 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole and phenyl isothiocyanate was worked up as above. The white solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol. Yield -75%, m.p. 203°. (Found: S; 20.25; $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$ requires S; 20.57), $\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})$; 1600 (C = N), 3350 (NH, broad).

***N'*-Phenyl *N*²-(pyridyl-2) thiocarbamide:** This compound was obtained in 70% yield from 2-amino pyridine and phenyl isothiocyanate. It was crystallised from ethanol. M.P. 171°. (Found: S; 13.68; $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires S; 13.97), $\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})$; 1600 (C = N) 3350 (NH broad).

2-(4'-Phenyl thiazolylimino-2') 3-phenyl 4-thiazolidinone: A mixture of thiocarbamide (3.1 g), mono chloroacetic acid (0.95 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (1 g) in glacial acetic acid was refluxed for a period of 5 hr during which it gave a clear solution. After cooling the solution was poured into cold water. The white solid, which appeared was washed with hot water to make it free from sodium acetate and finally crystallised from alcohol. Yield -65%.

M.P. 205°. (Found: C; 61.34, H; 3.52, N; 11.64, S; 18.12; $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}$ requires C; 61.53, H; 3.70, N; 11.96, S; 18.23), $\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})$; 1460 (CH_2 deformation), 1610 (C = N), 1700 (C = O), single spot in TLC in benzene acetic acid (4:1), $R_f -0.64$.

2-(Benzothiazolylimino-2') 3-phenyl 4-thiazolidinone: It was obtained in 70% yield from the corresponding thiocarbamide and mono chloro acetic acid; m.p. 185°. (Found: S; 19.45; $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2$ requires S; 19.69), $\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})$; 1475 (CH_2 deformation), 1610 (C = N), 1680 (C = O); single spot in TLC in benzene acetic acid (4:1), $R_f -0.62$.

2-(Pyridylimino-2') 3-phenyl 4-thiazolidinone: This compound was obtained as almost colourless crystal of M.P. 258° in 60% yield, from phenyl pyridyl thiocarbamide and mono chloro acetic acid. (Found: S; 11.54; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{SO}$ requires S; 11.89), $\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})$; 1460 (CH_2 deformation), 1700 (C = O). Single spot by TLC in benzene and acetic acid (4:1), $R_f -0.86$.

General procedure for the hydrolysis of thiazolidinones: The thiazolidinone (0.01M), rectified spirit (25 ml) and Conc. HCl (6 ml) were refluxed on a water bath for about 7-8 hr. Excess of alcohol was distilled off. The suspended residue was extracted with boiling water in order to separate the thiazolidinone which is insoluble in water. All the three thiazolidinones gave a white water insoluble residue corresponding to 3-phenyl 2, 4-thiazolidinone. M.P. 200°-201°. (Found: S; 16.35; $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{NSO}_2$ requires S; 16.57). The aqueous solution on basification by ammonia gave white crystalline solids corresponding to the melting points of the amines.

General procedure for the condensation of aldehydes with thiazolidinones: A mixture of thiazolidinone (0.01M) and aldehyde (0.01M) in glacial acetic acid (20-25 ml) and anhydrous sodium acetate (1 g) was refluxed for 5-6 hr. The coloured solution after cooling was poured into water. Orange to yellow coloured arylidene derivative were precipitated from different aldehydes. The precipitates were washed several times with hot water and finally crystallised from alcohol.

2-(4'-Phenyl thiazolylimino-2') 3-phenyl 5-benzal 4-thiazolidinone: This compound was obtained in 64% yield as yellow needles, m.p. 220°, $\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})$; 1610 (C = N), 1680 (C = O).

2-(Benzothiazolylimino-2') 3-phenyl 5-benzal 4-thiazolidinone: This was isolated in 55% yield as orange needles, m.p. 241°, $\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})$; 1610 (C = N), 1660 (C = O).

2-(Pyridylimino-2') 3-phenyl 5-benzal 4-thiazolidinone: From a mixture of 2-pyridylimino 3-phenyl thiazolidinone and benzaldehyde this compound was obtained as yellow needles, m.p. 226°. $\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})$; 1620 (C = N), 1690 (C = O).

General procedure for the bromination of arylidene derivatives of thiazolidinones: A solution of 2, 3-disubstituted thiazolidinone (0.001M) in chloroform (50 ml) was treated with bromine (0.001 M) in 5 ml of chloroform at 5° and the solution was kept in ice bath. In some cases red crystalline precipitate separated after 4-5 hr. In case of others the solution

TABLE I

ϕ	R	Arylidene derivatives (V)			Dibromides (VI)				
		M.P. °C	% Sulphur		M.P. °C	% Sulphur		% Bromine	
			Found	Calcd.		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Benzothiazolyl	Phenyl	241	15.26	15.49	193	11.05	11.17	27.61	27.92
-Do-	<i>p</i> -Methoxy phenyl	204	14.15	14.41	165	10.36	10.61	26.32	26.53
-Do-	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	227	14.18	14.31	235(d)	10.24	10.54	—	—
-Do-	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	255	12.78	13.00	200	9.32	9.50	—	—
Pyridyl	Phenyl	226	8.63	8.96	154	6.05	6.18	30.68	30.94
-Do-	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	238	8.10	8.26	146	5.75	5.85	29.42	29.25
-Do-	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	238	8.01	8.18	156	—	—	—	—
-Do-	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	230	7.23	7.33	240	5.26	5.36	—	—
-Do-	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	248	7.63	7.96	215	—	—	—	—
4-Phenyl thiazolyl	Phenyl	220	14.46	14.80	212	10.32	10.68	26.65	26.71
-Do-	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	162(d)	13.44	13.64	186	10.15	10.17	24.27	25.43
-Do-	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	173	13.37	13.53	203	10.06	10.11	—	—
-Do-	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	246(d)	12.16	12.35	250	9.28	9.43	—	—
-Do-	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	170	12.20	12.22	196	9.72	9.93	24.71	24.84

Yield varied from 40-65%, (d) denotes decomposition.

was concentrated under reduced pressure to get the precipitates. The precipitates were made soluble by passing SO₂ gas in their aqueous suspension and the resulting solutions were basified with ammonia to give the dibromo derivatives.

The physical and analytical data of different arylidene derivatives and their dibromo derivatives have been listed in Table 1.

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References

1. T. E. ACHARY and A. NAYAK, *Current Sci.*, 1972, **41**, 539.
2. P. N. DHAL, T. E. ACHARY, A. NAYAK and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **10**, 680.